

E-RIHS PP

CALL: H2020-INFRADEV-2016-2

TYPE OF ACTION: CSA

GA n.739503

D.9.2 ANALYSIS OF INNOVATION BACKGROUND

Lead Author: Mary Tehhan

With contributions from: Anthony Corns, Dimitrios Anglos, Michal Vopálenký, Sophia Sotiropoulou

Deliverable nature	Report (R)
Dissemination level	Confidential / Public / ...
Contractual delivery date	
Actual delivery date	
Version	0.9
Total page of number	55
Keywords	

ABSTRACT

The *'Analysis of The Innovation Background'* reviews the current innovation background for the E-RIHS partnership and assesses the existing heritage science innovation landscape. It discusses innovation as a general concept and more specifically in relation to RIs and Heritage Science. It traces good practices, successful examples and failures as well and examines strengths and limitations in different organizations within the E-RIHS partnership and beyond concerning innovation management and exploitation strategies. The role of the providers, the users and that of industry (including a definition of industry in relation to HS) is analysed. A set of key innovation indicators (KIIs) is presented that are intended to provide a tool for a measurable assessment of innovation in various stages of development.

This document is Deliverable 9.2, elaborated in the context of E-RIHS PP, WP-09, Task 9.2, *'Exploitation of E-RIHS capacities: innovation, transfer of knowledge and marketing'*. The analysis for this task was based on extensive qualitative and quantitative research. A series of expert interviews were conducted with participants of E-RIHS, and with experts external to the project (see annex). Two surveys were carried out:

- E-RIHS PP WP9.2 Innovation Survey
- ERIC's National Contact Points Innovation Survey

Deliverable 9.2 will be the analytic backbone of the Innovation Agenda, to be developed as part of WP9.2 by 2019.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project number	739503	Acronym	E-RIHS PP
Full title	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science – Preparatory Phase		
Project url	www.e-rihs.eu		
Document url			
EU Project Officer	Maria Theofilatou		

Deliverable	Number	D.9.2	Title	Analysis of Innovation Background
Work Package	Number	9	Title	Excellence and Innovation

Date of delivery	Contractual	M12	Actual	M16
Status	Version 0.9		Final	
Nature	<input type="checkbox"/> Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> Report <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> Other			
Dissemination level	<input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted			

Authors (Partner)	Mary Teehan, Anthony Corns, Dimitrios Anglos, Michal Vopálenký, Sophia Sotiropoulou			
Responsible Author	Name	Mary Teehan	Email	maryteehan@discoverprogramme.ie
	Partner	Discovery Programme	Phone	+353 1 639 3039

Abstract (for dissemination)	XXXXXXXXXX
Keywords	XXXXX, XXXXXX, XXXXXX, XXXXXX, XXXXXX

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev No.	Author	Change
00/00/0000	0.1	XXXXXX	

CONTENTS

Executive Summary	6
1. Excellence & Innovation	8
Overview	8
E-RIHS PP Phase	8
2. Innovation - Analyse it	9
What is Innovation	9
Types of Innovation	9
Levels of Impact	10
The Innovation Chain	12
Innovation Eco-systems	13
3. Innovation in context	14
Innovation in the Research Context	14
EU Policy and Funding Context	15
Smart Specialisation	15
National Level Overview	16
Weak Links for Exploitation	17
4. Research Infrastructures in the Innovation Chain	18
RIs as Innovation Hubs	18
Indicative Examples of Heritage Science Innovation	20
Directions for E-RIHS Innovations	22
5. Innovation Health Check	23
Facilitators	23
Inhibitors	24
6. Actors in Heritage Science Innovation	26
The role of providers - laboratories, research centres and clusters	26
The role of users in innovation development, use and exploitation	27
Industry in the field of Heritage Science	28
Industry as a user, as a partner or supplier	29
7. Innovation Analysis for E-RIHS Labs	32
E-RIHS PP 9.2 Innovation Survey – overview of results	32
Innovation Cases	34
8. Technology Transfer & Exploitation	38
Technology Transfer	38
Exploitation	40
9. Analysis of Management & Implementation Procedures	42
Approaches	42
Mercurial Model for Innovation Management	43
Innovation dissemination, societal impact and public engagement	43

	Key Performance Indicators	44
	Input KPIs	46
	Ongoing Continual KPIs	47
	Output KPIs	48
10.	Key Findings	50
11.	Methodology	52
12.	References	54

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1	Visualisation of Innovation Types through the Photographic Camera Lens	11
Figure 2	The Innovation Chain	12
Figure 3	Global Innovation Index - Location of Top 10 Innovation clusters	14
Figure 4	Top 3 Sources of Innovation Funding	16
Figure 5	ERIC's National Contact Points Innovation Survey findings on Systemic Policy Supports for EU Countries	16
Figure 6	Innovations Impact Analysis Ranking	22
Figure 7	Innovations Impact Visibility Analysis	22
Figure 8	Graphical representation of the Innovation Ecosystem and the interplay of actors in HS Innovation	27
Figure 9	WP9 Innovation Survey – Number of articles written by respondees in the cultural heritage field in last 5 years	28
Figure 10	Number of Collaborations with Industry by Organisations from the WP9.2 Innovation Survey	31
Figure 11	Innovation Survey results on most common areas where innovations are made	33
Figure 12	Innovation Survey findings on Organization support for facilitating innovation (Q15)	39
Figure 13	Graphical representation of efficiency of different innovation systems/environments	45

CASE STUDIES

Case Study 1	EMSO Incremental Innovation	19
Case Study 2	DARIAH ERIC Innovation Forum	28
Case Study 3	Success Story – Industry Collaboration with ARCHLAB & MOLAB	31
Case Study 4	Knowledge Transfer from Bio-medicine - NLO Microscopy	35
Case Study 5	University of Malaga's – Technology Transfer & Exploitation	40
Case Study 6	Dissemination - A link between ancient and modern Greece	43

ABBREVIATIONS

ARCHLAB	Consortium of Archives – part of IPERION CH
ARIADNE	Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives ERIC
CHARISMA	Cultural Heritage Advanced Research Infrastructures Multi-disciplinary Approach
CLARIN	European Research Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technology ERIC
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities ERIC
DIGILAB	Concept for access to provision of digital supports and repositories – part of E-RIHS project development
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor Observatory Infrastructure ERIC
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS PP	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science – Preparatory Phase
EuroArgo	European RI of ARGO - global network of marine profiling floats ERIC
EU-ARTECH	Access, Research and Technology for the conservation of the European Cultural Heritage
FIXLAB	Access provision to fixed laboratory equipment and expertise – part of IPERION CH
ESFRI	European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructures
ESS	European Social Survey ERIC
FP7/8/9	European Funding Framework Programme 7/8/9
GRI	Global Research Infrastructure
HS	Heritage Science
IPERION CH	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure on Cultural Heritage
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KET	Key Enabling Technologies
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MOLAB	Access provision to mobile laboratory of equipment and expertise – part of IPERION CH
NEI	Non-economic innovation
NTI	Non-technological innovation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RI	Research Infrastructure
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe ERIC
SI	Social innovation
TTO	Technology Transfer Office
TI	Technological innovation
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The goal of E-RIHS, the *European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science*, is to grow and strengthen a creative, European-wide framework for supporting frontier research in heritage science. It will do so by offering access to expertise, data and technologies through a standardized approach based on different modes of services organized in four platforms:

- ARCHLAB (access to heritage archives and collections);
- DIGILAB (remote access to data and tools for heritage research);
- FIXLAB (access to large-scale facilities and advanced laboratories);
- MOLAB (collections of mobile instruments enabling in-situ diagnostics).

The success and long-term sustainability of E-RIHS will rely on its capacity and means to foster scientific excellence and equally to **identify, promote** and **exploit** its innovation potential. This will enable the development of next generation instruments, methods and knowledge management tools capable of advancing the state of the art across the RI.

The main objective of the work in Deliverable 9.2, '*Analysis of The Innovation Background*', is to map the innovations developed in heritage science and to analyse the role of the main actors involved. This includes the framework conditions as to how to provide novel and efficient access services and offering unique research opportunities to a broad spectrum of user communities, including industry.

Firstly, an overview of basic concepts relevant to the growth of Innovation and innovation eco-systems is provided. Open innovation is key to future directions. Considering E-RIHS will be the most multi-disciplinary ERIC and that innovation concepts are largely economically based, it is key to understand how and where a heritage science research infrastructure can exploit innovation systems. Analysis of future policy directions indicate that the innovation landscape into which E-RIHS will be born is receptive to a trans-disciplinary, trans-sectoral and geographic reach of E-RIHS could be successfully exploited for innovation supports. Bringing the experience of innovations by the sciences to the co-creative and holistic directions of cultural heritage research are positive.

Innovation through smart specialisation methodologies in E-RIHS, could be applied in locating LABS – for example, how FIXLAB facilities differentiate themselves and how can they specialise may decide on their E-RIHS location. This could significantly contribute to the sustainability of the E-RIHS brand of excellence.

Funding was found to be largely nationally based. Thus, when national feasibility of E-RIHS membership is being assessed, the added value rewards through innovation technology transfer and exploitation should be encouraged as a high-impact pillar on which to base decisions.

E-RIHS will have a significant role, as a research infrastructure (RI), as a hub for innovation. Various types of innovation stem from the operation of RI's, which can be viewed on the basis of how these innovations were generated (research- or use-led), how they propagated (knowledge spill over, technology transfer) or what framework they grew in (clustering or systemic). While there exist numerous good cases of inventions generated by researchers working in RIs, a structured or induced approach to innovation is a relatively recent occurrence in the context of RI ecosystems. Prioritising solutions to

non-economic innovation must be considered, given the limitations on revenue to ERIC's. E-RIHS will have to operate in such a fluid environment and foster innovations in a broad context encompassing:

- technical & methodological
- non-economic
- non-technological
- social innovations

To ensure the E-RIHS innovation ecosystem grows in a balanced way, the role of the main players in the RI, namely the access providers, the users and the broader heritage industry was carefully analysed with respect to the combined contributions of these actors to developing innovation. A unique feature of E-RIHS is the user-provider interaction. It has the potential of generating innovation in co-development of next generation instruments, methods or knowledge management tools for advancing the state of the art across the heritage science domain. Industry is considered as a key player in the development and the future of RI's. However, in the case of E-RIHS, 'Industry' needs to be considered with a wider view to include those outside of pure academia with revenue/ commercial potential. In this context, all cultural institutions can be considered as specific 'industries'.

Through a health check analysis, the main facilitators and inhibitors relevant to E-RIHS have been identified. How to cultivate the former and suppress the latter have been outlined. These factors are relevant to the growth and sustainability of E-RIHS and will have to be considered in the context of the Innovation Agenda.

Issues of technology transfer and exploitation for E-RIHS are outlined. The protection of IPR was identified as a critical for any innovation exploitation. In this respect, the connection of researchers to Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) in a national-hub level is important. While a central E-RIHS TTO would have the role of collecting information and promoting best practices for exploitation.

The most significant findings were made via the WP9.2 Innovation Survey and the ERIC National Contact Point Innovation Survey. A detailed analysis of unfulfilled needs in the heritage science sphere are outlined in consideration of the four E-RIHS LABS future directions

1. New methodologies
2. New instrumentation
3. Knowledge transfer
4. User services

Finally, analysis of common approaches for managing and setting up procedures for implementing innovation demonstrate that adaptability is crucial for effective management. A 'mercurial' model based on such flexibility is most appropriate for coordinating the innovation chain in E-RIHS. Implementation of such a model would need to use an E-RIHS tailored Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) toolkit to monitor and respond to its unique research innovation landscape. The innovation eco-system of E-RIHS, will need a smooth infrastructure, enabling providers, users and industry as actors from idea generation towards fruition.

Deliverable 9.2 will be the analytic backbone of the Innovation Agenda, to be developed as part of WP9.2 by 2019.

1. EXCELLENCE & INNOVATION

Overview

E-RIHS, the *European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science*, represents a major initiative towards an advanced concept for a pan-European Research Infrastructure capable of delivering top-level cross-disciplinary services to users and promoting innovation in heritage science^{1, 2, 3, 4}. Via the integration of world-leading European resources, E-RIHS aims at creating an organisation with a clear identity and a strong cohesive role within the global heritage science community.

The mission of E-RIHS is to ambitiously stretch the boundaries and the impact of heritage science. It will develop the most comprehensive and advanced scientific and technological capabilities, that will enable researchers, organizations and industry to develop skills, knowledge and innovation to enable the appreciation and preservation of heritage. Emphasis will be placed on promoting a culture of cross-disciplinary collaboration and training throughout its member states.

E-RIHS will deliver integrated access to expertise, data and technologies through a standardized approach. It will promote best practice and advance methods for the specific needs of heritage assets, whether material or digital. This will be implemented on the basis of different modes of access:

- ARCHLAB - access to heritage archives and collections;
- DIGILAB -remote access to data and tools for heritage research;
- FIXLAB - access to large-scale facilities and advanced laboratories;
- MOLAB - collections of mobile instruments enabling in-situ diagnostics.

E-RIHS PP Phase

E-RIHS, since March 2016, is one of the six new projects incorporated into the ESFRI Roadmap, and currently the only Research Infrastructure project in the Social and Cultural Innovation section. The ESFRI Recommendation on the E-RIHS proposal for the ESFRI 2016 Roadmap cited a ‘very high’ scientific relevance and impact case, based on E-RIHS responding to “... *needs of those involved in heritage science, adding capacities, while overcoming disciplinary boundaries and providing wider access to relevant research and innovation*”⁵.

E-RIHS Preparatory Phase (E-RIHS PP, H2020-INFRADEV-2016-2017, GA no 739503) was launched in 2017 and will last until 2020. The main goal of the preparatory phase is to address governance, scientific strategy, financial aspects, and the legal documents of the infrastructure.

In the framework of E-RIHS PP, Work Package 9 (WP-09) focuses on two major aspects ‘Excellence and Innovation’. As stated in the E-RIHS PP description of work, “*Fostering scientific excellence and promoting innovation are essential ingredients to supporting frontier research in heritage science. In this context, E-RIHS shall have to play a leading role in identifying key areas, where opportunities for performing innovative research arise. This will enable the development of next generation instruments, methods and knowledge management tools capable of advancing the state of the art across the RI, introducing novel and efficient access services and offering unprecedented research opportunities to a broad spectrum of user communities, including industry*” The work in WP-09 is distributed in two Tasks. Task 9.1 concentrates on ‘*Excellence: priorities and strategy*’ and the goal is to produce the first version of the E-RIHS Scientific Vision (Deliverable 9.1⁶, Already delivered: 08/03/2018) and subsequently to prepare the E-RIHS Scientific Strategy document (Deliverable 9.3). In parallel,

Task 9.2, ‘*Exploitation of E-RIHS capacities: innovation, transfer of knowledge and marketing*’ aims to explore the present innovation landscape of E-RIHS (Deliverable 9.2: Analysis of the Innovation Background) and identify and suggest pathways for continuing and enhancing the innovation potential and output of E-RIHS, preparing the Innovation Agenda (Deliverable 9.4).

2. INNOVATION - ANALYSE IT

What is Innovation

Numerous interpretations have been given to the term ‘innovation’, depending on technology, application or the market context. It centres on associated socio-economic impact. Based on the widely accepted term introduced in the Oslo Manual⁷: “*An innovation is the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organisational method in business practices, workplace organisation or external relations*”. Innovation can be considered as the tool that can lead to sustainable growth and competitiveness through value creation, tackling societal challenges, creating new jobs and increasing employment⁸.

The concept of Innovation is rooted in the discipline of economics in the 1940’s. In Schumpeter’s view, innovation is the fruition of invention⁹. The application to market of a product, process or service invention, causing radical, incremental, modular or architectural change becomes the innovation. Such applied changes have traditionally been driven by revenue reward. On the other hand, Kline’s chain-linked model of innovation focuses on first identifying an unfulfilled need, then solving it through creation of a product, process or service¹⁰. This later model from the 1980’s is in fact the one that has encouraged investment in Research & Development. It has resulted in monies at State level to grow the commercialisation capacity of the sciences, often in collaboration with the industries which may benefit from it. Innovation approaches in the EU now operate to a large extent on the ‘Open Innovation’¹¹ approach, developed by Chesbrough in 2003¹². This brings innovation actors across organisational, sectoral and geographical boundaries together in developing and diffusing ideas, moving away from closed internally-biased innovation.

Types of Innovation

In an attempt to characterize the different types of innovations, a widely used approach views innovation from two perspectives:

- a. the **use or application** of the innovation and
- b. the **degree of novelty** introduced by the innovation.

The use or application context can be further distinguished into: **product**, **process** or **service** innovation.

- A **product innovation** (see radical innovation example) is the introduction of a new or significantly improved product or service or the introduction of a new use for an already existing product. The introduced changes may refer to improvements in technical specifications, components and materials, software, ease of use or other functions.
- A **process innovation** (see modular innovation example) refers to significant changes in techniques, equipment and/or software that lead to the introduction of a new or significantly improved production or delivery method.

It can be further distinguished to:

Production methods (referring to techniques, equipment and software used to produce goods or services, for instance, the implementation of new automation equipment on a production line or the implementation of computer-assisted design for product development)

Delivery methods (concerning logistics of a firm, and for instance, equipment, software and techniques used to source inputs, allocate supplies or deliver final products).

- A **service innovation** (see architectural innovation example) implies the use of a new service or a significant improvement of an existing service, which is put into practice and provides benefit to the organization that has developed it or makes use of it.

Levels of Impact

Distinctions of impact levels of innovation, as per Henderson and Clark¹³, uses a novelty based typology. They define four types of innovation that can influence a product, method or service as follows (see Fig. 1).

- **Incremental innovation:** it improves a product or technology by introducing key changes in core components (see Case Study1);
- **Modular innovation:** refers to the use of different core components within an existing system or design;
- **Architectural innovation:** implies the introduction of a re-designed or re-configured system while maintaining its core components;
- **Radical innovation:** introduces a completely new design through the novel use of components.

Radical or Disruptive innovation

The first camera sold to the public was named the 'Kodak' in 1888 and was pioneered by George Eastman. It was a very simple box camera, with a fixed-focus lens and single shutter speed and came pre-loaded with enough film for 100 exposures but needed to be returned to Kodak for processing when the roll was finished and then reloaded with a new film. Although photographic techniques such as 'camera obscura' preceded this, its availability for mass purchase and the consequent burgeoning of movie films was a disruptive innovation.

Incremental innovation

Single-lens Reflex (SLR) cameras were around since 1928. Incremental changes after WWII set the standard for SLR's for decades. The eye-level viewfinder, appeared on the Hungarian Duflex in 1947. Prior to this, all SLRs were equipped with waist-level focusing screens. The Duflex was also the first SLR with an instant-return mirror, which prevented the viewfinder from being blacked out after each exposure.

Modular Innovation

With the introduction of the Polaroid Model 95 – also known as the Land Camera after its inventor - in 1948, different core components were used for an entirely new type of camera. This was the world's first viable instant-picture camera. It used a patented chemical process to produce finished positive prints from the exposed negatives in under a minute. Innovations were made to the process of picture development.

Architectural Innovation

The first phone with a built-in camera was manufactured by Samsung in 2000. The SCH-V200 flipped open to reveal the built-in digital camera capable of taking 20 photos at 0.35-megapixels. It has changed how we interact with cameras, photography and phones.

Figure 1: Visualisation of Innovation Types through the Photographic Camera Lens

The Innovation Chain

While clever or novel ideas are the core of innovation, they are not themselves sufficient to generate a new product, unless a proper framework or chain of steps is set in place. The innovation chain is indeed a milestone concept developed by Hansen and Birkinshaw¹⁴ for effective innovation management. It puts structure on the process of transforming ideas into outputs as an integrated flow. The first of the three phases in the chain is to **generate ideas**; this can happen inside a unit, across units in a company, or outside the firm. The second phase is to **convert ideas**, or, more specifically, select ideas for funding and develop them into products, processes or services. The third is to **diffuse** those products, processes and services.

Figure 2: The Innovation Chain

Ideally, a circle of learning is then created to provide feedback on how to continue improved application of the innovation. Counter-intuitively, they reject the wholesale importation of 'innovation best-practices'. The key to innovation is seeking out the weakest link in the chain. This approach merges with Kline's model of innovation in 'identifying unresolved needs' first.

The innovation chain is a valuable concept for RI's, as complex eco-systems of creation. E-RIHS, if designated as an ERIC, will likely be one of the most multi-disciplinary ERICs. The innovation chain within such a multi-faceted ERIC will need a smooth infrastructure, enabling providers, users and industry as actors from idea generation towards fruition. Identifying a clear process can help with the successful implementation of innovation management by focusing time and resources on weakest links.

Innovation Eco-systems

Innovation ecosystems are considered as the optimum mix of interactions between performers that can transform an idea into a solution or bring a product or service forward into the market. They usually derive from economic, social, ecological or political challenges that are tackled within an ecosystem of centres of knowledge, research performers and research facilitators, industries, entrepreneurs, citizens and governments that interact productively within the lines of complexity, cooperation, competence, competition and communication.¹⁵

The essential components of the innovation process can be categorized as follows¹⁶ :

- **Human resources:** Highly skilled personnel with the required expertise for the generation of new ideas and the development of new products that will lead innovation;
- **Funding:** Appropriate economic resources, public or private, that can finance innovation actions;
- **Advice and Support Services:** High added value support services that cover all steps of the innovation chain; and
- **Knowledge and Intellectual Property:** A pool of innovative ideas and expertise able to produce innovation opportunities.

Of particular note for RI's, as an innovation eco-system, is that users can no longer be considered as an inanimate part of this process. User expertise should be nurtured for idea generation to diffusion stages in the innovation chain. In the business world, a Finnish Innovation Evaluation study found there are active initiatives to seek out “unaroused and unarticulated user needs”¹⁷ . They do this through extensive observation and interaction. Crowd-sourcing – obtaining information or input to an initiative from a large group of people typically via the internet - engages users in idea generation, applications and content. In a multi-disciplinary RI such as E-RIHS, providing communication platforms could induce participation in the innovation eco-system by the users.

Significant potential for innovation can lie with the users evolving into providers. Becoming a provider to a co-creation eco-system means, that not just the need but the critical capacity exists to justify it. In the case of E-RIHS, for instance, users of MOLAB may create or refine portable equipment for applying a specific technique to a particular type of object. This idea may have been generated from unfulfilled needs in existing MOLAB's. Innovation eco-systems provide a system where such unfulfilled needs translate into research areas. Identifying these gaps will be worked on in tandem with E-RIHS Scientific Agenda, Catalogue of Resources and Services and Sustainability Plan and produced in the Innovation Agenda.

In essence, the attractiveness of these eco-systems is the flexibility offered within a structure. The co-creation paradigm, or clustering of actors, increases the odds of idea generation, eases the path of converting the idea to application and diffusion. E-RIHS is a potential innovation eco-system. Application of an innovation chain infrastructure is advised to unlock the huge potential in contributing to the E-RIHS brand of excellence.

3. INNOVATION IN CONTEXT

Innovation in the Research Context

E-RIHS will be geographically located in the world's prime 'innovation location'. From 2015 – 2017, eight of the top ten global innovators in the world are in Europe¹⁸ (see Fig. 3) . In 2017, of the top twenty global innovators:

- 65% of highest R&D spenders,
- 65% of research & industry collaborations,
- 65% of full-time employees in research per 1 million of population

were all in Europe. This places E-RIHS in the optimum co-creation eco-system.

Often, innovation indicators are economically-based, for example, patent growth. So how can a non-economic body such as the E-RIHS ERIC approach innovation in the future? Key to the way forward is to:

- a. map the national and EU policy and funding future and
- b. understand the weak links of non-economic innovations for heritage science.

Understanding the innovation landscape for E-RIHS in the future requires an analysis of the policy context within which it will operate. Currently there are strong innovation supports for systemic innovation in science and commercial spheres. Only in 2018 has there been investigation into innovation for cultural heritage research, stemming from outcomes for European Year of Cultural Heritage 2018.

Figure 3: Global Innovation Index - Location of Top 10 Innovation clusters

EU Policy and Funding Context

Support for systemic innovation began in the 1990's with FP4 and FP5. This has gradually diversified and strengthened. The adoption of the Europe 2020 strategy and the Innovation Union flagship initiative in 2010 influenced the structure of FP8, which was adopted in 2013 and Horizon 2020 was its biggest stream. With Horizon 2020, FP8 covered all aspects of the innovation process. However, complexity in the management and implementation brought about a new level of fragmentation at EU level regarding the funding of innovation-related activities. Looking at **trends for FP9** under which E-RIHS hopes to operate, the European Parliamentary Research Service highlights several issues that will have to be addressed from FP8:

- the lack of clarity regarding the EU innovation policy that the FP is expected to implement
- the balance between the various aspects of the innovation process - research being just one of these
- evaluation of the EU added value of the FP and its components, justifying support for each of these aspects;
- assessment of the existing instruments and their efficiency at EU level to rationalise the EU funding landscape and limit fragmentation;
- the balance between collaborative action and single beneficiary measures, the share of which has increased sharply in recent FPs;
- the balance between a focus on excellence that results in the concentration of innovation capacity and efforts to reduce the innovation gap with countries and regions requesting more cohesion measures
- the balance between top-down and bottom-up approaches when defining the programme's priorities¹⁹.

Horizon 2020 was intended to allocate 3% of EU GDP to innovation. However, the economic crisis has stymied investment levels. And so FP9 will have a strong impetus to finally achieve this. Together with increased funding for social science and humanities since FP6, emphasis on more holistic collaborations and suggestions of a 'mission' based FP following H2020, the multi-disciplinarity of E-RIHS will be well placed to benefit from **FP9**, which will have a **projected budget of € 114.8 billion**²⁰. **The 3 O's policy - Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World**, published in 2016²¹ - focuses on aspects of innovation in research but is not straightforward for innovation implementation in research infrastructures. It is citizen-centric, encouraging disruptive open innovation. Stronger engagement to expand user experiences is also a predominant theme.

Smart Specialisation

Smart specialisation is a regional policy framework for innovation driven growth. The concept that aims to boost regional innovation, contributing to growth and prosperity by helping and enabling regions to focus on their strengths. The EU Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3)²² connect broader policy areas such as R&I with cohesion policy, EU value chains and other areas. It focuses policy on where a region can differentiate and specialise for innovation success. For example, in Ireland the smart specialisation approach has manifested itself in R&I by the publication of National Research Priority Areas 2018 - 2023²³. Those priorities overlap with the national Innovation 2020 Agenda pillars, Horizon 2020 work plan areas, EU and global value chains. For innovation in E-RIHS, this methodology could be applied in locating LABS – how FIXLAB facilities differentiate themselves and how can they specialise may decide on their E-RIHS location.

Smart specialisation (SS) for ERIHS should also be considered with caution. The differentiation and specialisation approach for heritage science would place itself outside of the remit of many SS national plans. For example, in Ireland E-RIHS would have to align itself by side-stepping into ICT, Materials & Manufacturing, Climate Change or Innovation in Services, which are just some of the six main Irish research priorities.

National Level Overview

As a leader on the **Global Innovation Index**, Europe has strong innovation supports and policies on a national level. This is noteworthy, as in the WP9.2 Innovation Survey it was found that the predominant source of financial support for innovation is accessed at a national level (see Fig. 4). And while internal organisational funding was ranked second, some of this could be considered indirect national funding as research organisations often benefit from national operations grants. Therefore, when justifying national membership for E-RIHS, demonstrating the added-value to be received from E-RIHS as an innovation focused RI should be a core component of membership feasibility.

A separate survey was conducted of 14 ERIC's National Contact Points (NCP's) across Europe to collate an overarching insight into the innovation landscape into which E-RIHS will be born. Almost all countries surveyed had national innovation strategies and 72% had specific policies for RI's (see Fig. 5). Interestingly, 100% of the respondents' national innovation offices were located in their Ministry of Research, as opposed to Business or Culture Departments. The Netherlands and Iceland are two exceptions to this, as innovation is located within a Ministry also responsible for Culture. The lack of innovation supports, from a cultural heritage point of view, may hold future opportunities for E-RIHS innovation implementation processes. Although there are robust national supports in place, the NCP's felt that inadequate organisational and governmental supports were still the strongest inhibitors of innovation in general while poor levels of external communication and collaboration were seen as the most significant inhibitors to RI's specifically.

Fig.4: Top 3 Sources of Innovation Funding

Fig. 5: ERIC's National Contact Points Innovation Survey findings on Systemic Policy Supports for EU Countries

Weak Links for Exploitation

Honing in on specific issues for RI's, the development of the EC **Long-term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures** report saw a great challenge for RI's was "... to put the third "O" - Open Innovation - alongside the open science and open data capability and capacity which H2020 RI is helping to realise"²⁴. In order to unlock their potential for innovation, RI's are asked to address continuing weak links in the research value chain, such as:

- open access and data provision
- mobility of expertise and the right time and in the right place
- creating publically exploited services for citizen needs
- working with business and industry for the both economic and public needs
- involving national and EU bodies in the expansion of RI's at both levels
- creating systemic support services and resources for innovation within RI's
- RI's at the forefront of scientific excellence²⁵

These are areas for non-economic innovations in E-RIHS. While the reward for innovation in industry is revenue, RI's seek recognition for sustainability of such excellence. Association of the E-RIHS brand will be part of excellence recognition. However, incentivising excellence by innovating in the above key areas is more likely to find policy and financial support for E-RIHS's future.

The '3 O's' do not directly address heritage. However, **Innovation in Cultural Heritage** was launched in March 2018 in the context of European Year of Cultural Heritage²⁶. This is a long needed document which will direct cultural heritage research at a European level. While the report specifically refers to innovation in its title, it does not translate into systemic innovation systems in heritage research, as directly addressed in the Open Innovation policy. There are suggestions for change and areas for development, rather than how to apply new ideas. Most significantly, it concludes that amongst potential research needs are:

- Co-creative methods to bring heritage stakeholders, practitioners and academics together in the definition and recognition of European cultural heritage
- A holistic research agenda to stimulate the professional institutionalisation of heritage studies/ heritage sciences

A key concept put forward classifies how, when and why heritage research has evolved gone from a focus on national narratives in the 19th century (referred to as the First Regime), onto World Heritage (the Second Regime) into holistic approaches encouraged today (the Third Regime). As the most multi-disciplinary ERIC, E-RIHS will be a practical application of this Third Regime and may open the door for more systemic innovation to cultural heritage domain.

Strategic operational policies for research infrastructures have placed a strong emphasis on innovation as a key for their sustainability. At a national level, EU countries have a strong policy support for innovation – the majority of member states have a specific innovation strategy or policy. It is notable that, with the exception of Iceland and the Netherlands, innovation is not placed with culture related ministries but with those responsible for research, education and/ or business and enterprise.

In essence, these policies will formulate the E-RIHS goals towards innovation and excellence. Cohesion between existing resources and human capital, working in partnerships with industry and placing the user as part of the innovation cycle in heritage science should be core to E-RIHS Innovation Agenda.

Other countries outside of Europe, particularly the E-RIHS observer members and those who are developing new strategies and research roadmaps, should be encouraged to consider heritage science and E-RIHS as an enabler of the **UN Sustainable Development Goals**²⁷ .

The national and global landscape will be receptive to E-RIHS, as a structure. Key findings from the Global Innovation Index analysis for 2017 support the RI as an innovation enabler, finding that “Regional clusters of inventive activity are essential to national innovation performance”²⁸ . However, it also suggests that improved innovation metrics on this topic are required. On a national level there is a lot to learn in both the monitoring of innovation and in tackling new challenges in human capital, knowledge exchange and Key Enabling Technologies (KET’s). Focusing on non-economic innovation areas for E-RIHS is crucial to sustainability of the ERIC.

4. RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES IN THE INNOVATION CHAIN

RIs as Innovation Hubs

Research Infrastructures (RIs) are major players in the research and innovation system. They enable demand driven research and contribute significantly to addressing global and societal challenges. A most important aspect of RIs is their role as the convergence point of researchers, funding bodies, industry and even governments. The ERIC entities – single sited, distributed and virtual – are growing in significance as EU innovation hubs. They provide a platform from which to face cross disciplinary scientific and technical challenges of great importance, often beyond just the realm of pure science and technology. RIs allow access to equipment and facilities, data, archives and collections, hence are considered as genuine generators of innovation. Furthermore, RIs are innovation enablers through different types of strategic co-operations (e.g. industrial, cross-disciplinary and regional)²⁹ .

Various types of innovation³⁰ stem from the operation of RI’s, which can be viewed on the basis of how they were generated, how they propagated or what environment they grew in. For example, we can identify innovations as:

- Use – led: originating from the demand of user communities to address certain grand challenges;
- Research-based: coming up as a result of basic or applied research;
- Knowledge spillovers: resulting from knowledge generated in one field or discipline moving over to a different field because of its capacity to solve a different problem or satisfy a different need;
- Technology transfer: arising from technical solutions becoming available to a broader community of users;
- Clustering and agglomeration effects: developing as a result of broad collaborations among similar type of RI’s and related players (including research labs, SME’s and industry) and
- Systemic innovation: referring to a much wider framework that promotes interaction among many parties cultivating a culture of co-creation that can generate significant breakthroughs.

While there are numerous good cases of inventions generated by researchers working in RIs, a structured or induced approach to innovation is a relatively recent occurrence in the context of RI ecosystems. As a part of the consultation for the *Long-term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures 2017 Report*, it was discovered that 64.3% of the RI respondents declared not having an Innovation Advisory Committee in place³¹. When some of the 15 operational ERIC's were evaluated for this analysis – DARIAH, ESS, CESSDA, EuroArgo, EMSO – they state that they have no formal innovation infrastructure. The ERIC's National Contact Points Innovation Survey found that an average of 30% of RI's they represented had an innovation policy or dedicated member of staff. However, innovation practice of taking an idea generated to application does occur on a more organic or project basis, such as the EMSO ERIC project to drive innovation in between a cluster of related RI's (see Case Study 1).

According to the same report, a major prerequisite for achieving sustainability is: “...unlocking the innovation potential of RI”. However, the report identifies certain issues within RI's which stymie innovation. Some of the challenges involve flawed frameworks for interaction with industry and differing perceived objectives between academia and industry. For example, CERN is cited as the origin for the idea to transform the academic internet into the World Wide Web but it was not involved in its commercialization. The difference between the two is that CERN is an RI driven by curiosity and research excellence; industry is driven by revenue. The challenge for E-RIHS is to foster such innovations while finding a reasonable model to devolve commercialization aspects to the national or industry level.

Case Study 1: EMSO Incremental Innovation

ENVRIPLUS is a cluster of research infrastructures for Environmental and Earth System sciences, built around the ESFRI roadmap and bringing leading e-infrastructures and Integrating activities together with technical specialist partners. ENVRIPLUS is driven by 3 overarching goals:

1. favoring cross-fertilization between infrastructures
2. implementing innovative concepts and devices across RIs
3. facilitating research and innovation in the field of environment to an increasing number of users outside the RIs.

Image © ENVRIPLUS

Indicative Examples of Heritage Science Innovation

The examples illustrated, show the diverse potential of RIs for fostering innovation – products, processes and services - and at the same time demonstrate the need to position the RI's properly within the innovation chain so as to enhance and exploit this potential further.

1. Use Led Innovation

MOLAB when created in 2003 was an innovative concept in itself. Since 2003, seven (7) mobile scientific analytical techniques such as XRF, Raman and FTIR, t-resolved fluorescence spectroscopies have been available.

Incremental changes have been driven by needs of the user.

Through IPERION CH, eight (8) MOLABs operate currently in the EU.

When interacting with users, there were difficulties with software compatibility of MOLAB and user systems. Therefore, the MOVIDA software was developed and is used to access MOLAB analytic outputs (see more on the MOLAB's advancement in Annex 1).

Image © IPERION CH MOLAB Project

2. Research Based Innovation

Research at the Vilnius University Laser Research Center on the interactions of ultra-short laser pulses with materials has led to the creation of FEMTIKA, a spin-off company, to supply the growing demands worldwide for tools and technologies enabling true 3D laser fabrication, with custom design components in micro- and sub micro scale. The company focuses on the design and manufacturing of custom 3D laser precision processing systems appropriate for fabrication of 3D micro- and nano-structures and the rapid replication of laser produced 2D and 2.5D structures.

Image © Femtika, www.femtika.lt

3. Knowledge Spillovers Innovation

Researchers at a Materials Institute (NCSR "Demokritos" and Technical Univ. of Crete, Greece) in their investigation of the mechanism by which oxalate salts protect stone monument surfaces, a novel formulation that has been marketed by a company in Greece as a consolidator of building surfaces. The knowledge from this research can now be used in the construction sector for smarter building conservation and protection (see related information in Annex 1, I.Karatassios interview).

4. Technology Transfer

ASCENT - EU Nanoelectronics Network. A collaboration of IMEC (Leuven, B), CEA - Leti Technological Research Division (Genoble, F) and Tyndall National Institute (Cork, I) (coordinating access office) was established ca. 2015 from a need to provide academia with nano-technology lab access. Industry accessed such instrumentation at a cost of up to € 12,000 per day but such costs inhibited academic nano research.

ASCENT provides free access time in 3 countries. They have a policy of minimising application time frames to weeks rather than months, leading to process innovations. Research innovations have radically reduced nano-chip components size to 5-10 nm.

E-RIHS could benefit from this model of interaction with industry as a supplier of access, and also in the short decision-making time for research users.

Image © ASCENT Network

5. Clustering and agglomeration effects

The European Cluster of Advanced Laser Light Sources (EUCALL) is a network between leading large-scale user facilities for free-electron laser, synchrotron and optical laser radiation and their users. Under EUCALL, they work together on their common methodologies and research opportunities, and develop tools to sustain this interaction in the future.

EUCALL has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and involves 11 partners from nine countries as well as the networks LaserLab Europe and FELs of Europe during the project period 2015 to 2018. This Open Innovation approach enables a highly efficiency innovation chain, from idea generation to provider and user.

Image © www.eucall.eu

6. Systemic Innovation

The Fast Track to Innovation (FTI), launched in 2017, is a fully-bottom-up innovation support programme promoting close-to-the-market innovation activities open to industry-driven consortia that can be composed of all types of participants. It can help partners to co-create and test breakthrough products, services or business processes that have the potential to revolutionise existing or create entirely new markets, under the helm of the new European Innovation Council (EIC) pilot. Systemic innovation refers, most often, to existence of a co-ordinated innovation system, such as enabling frameworks of policy, people and programmes for innovation chains.

Image © EU Commission

Directions for E-RIHS Innovations

And so, we must ask what other areas and ways of innovation can be enabled. Analysis of the WP9.2 Innovation Survey shows that human capacity building, societal, policy/ public service impacts were the three most significant innovations outcomes of innovations made. Economic impacts were fourth (see Fig. 6). When asked where innovations were most visible, new techniques, service provision and access provision were most significant. The commercial areas of patents and spin-off companies were least visible (see also Fig.12 in Section 7). Therefore, E-RIHS has the potential to also create:

- non-economic (NEI) – professional processes
- technological (TI) – enabling software
- non-technological (NTI) – understanding societal attitudes towards, for example, artefacts
- social innovations (SI) – informing public policy

The Citizen is increasingly being placed at the heart of research, and consequently, RI's. Generating and deploying processes, products and services with a social value and, if needed, onto markets through industry is a healthier relationship that avoids stagnation. More balanced and open partnerships with industry are needed. A shift in mind-set between the RI's, academia and industry is also advised, along with stronger communication for added-value in an RI such as E-RIHS.

ERICs were legislated for in 2009. Innovation on the research landscape became a core component of the EU agenda for Research & Development investment from 2008 onwards in an economic downturn, demonstrating a truth of innovative activity that 'necessity is the mother of invention'. It is only recently that ESFRI specified innovation as an ERIC designation consideration.

ERICs, as an RI, work within specific boundaries concerning economic activity. Article 3.1 states: ³²

“An ERIC shall pursue its principal tasks on a non-economic basis. However, it may carry out limited economic activities closely related to its task, provided that they are closely related to its principal task and that they do not jeopardise the achievement thereof.”

ERICs cannot earn over 25% of a yearly budget without having to create a spin-off company for that source of revenue. This eliminates the involvement E-RIHS can have in the innovation chain to areas of idea generation and conversion to venture. Diffusion to markets for E-RIHS will be the role of national or industry organisations, upon agreed terms.

Fig. 6: Innovations Impact Analysis Ranking

Fig. 7: Innovations Impact Visibility Analysis

5. INNOVATION HEALTH CHECK

Innovation and how or if it develops depends on a range of appropriate framework conditions. These conditions should be such that they favour progress towards innovative results and at the same time minimize obstacles. As a result, it turns out to be very important to identify facilitators as well inhibitors along the innovation chain and try to manage them properly. Of highest relevance to E-RIHS are the following:

Facilitators

Innovation depends on a range of framework conditions. Of highest relevance to E-RIHS are the following:

1. **Personal curiosity** - academic curiosity and excellence lead to discovery of the unexpected. Facilitating tangible applications from new discoveries in, and through, heritage science is vital.
2. **Finance** - access to finance is a key driver of all stages of the innovation chain (see Figure 6) – from idea generation stage, through to selection, application and diffusion. Finance is a consideration for internal processes – such as labour for technology transfer – and external collaborations. Indirectly, E-RIHS can be a factor in why other projects are funded, by access to the E-RIHS established brand of excellence. The more innovative that E-RIHS is, the more attractive it is to financial supports.
3. **Skills for innovation** - skilled labour plays a key role in innovation by generating new knowledge, adopting and adapting existing ideas to develop incremental innovations, and identifying relevant opportunities. Various different skills are required for innovation: technical skills; “soft” skills (e.g. ability to communicate, to work and interact in teams and heterogeneous groups); entrepreneurial skills (e.g. competences in risk assessment and strategic thinking, self-confidence, and ability to make the best of personal networks). Skills mismatches may result from a gap between the demand for and the supply of skills. The demand for skills is affected by technological progress (e.g. the expansion of ICTs increases the demand for digital-age literacy skills); labour market conditions (e.g. mobility of skilled workers); and specialization, organization, and innovative process and culture (e.g. some bodies may tend to collaborate with other organizations to access specific skills, while others may prefer to hire people and internally develop these specific skills). The supply of skilled personnel is shaped by a country’s education system, firms’ involvement in employees training, and migration of skilled labour. Education policies can serve the need for diverse and complex skills in innovative activities.
4. **Intellectual property rights (IPR)** - the intellectual property system plays a critical role in innovation. Intellectual property rights, such as patents, trademarks, designs and copyrights, give innovators ownership of their knowledge creations and can facilitate the transfer of knowledge and technologies. They may also have multiple other functions, such as signaling current and prospective value to investors down the innovation chain, accessing knowledge markets and networks, and facilitating the disclosure of information on inventions. This is of most relevance to E-RIHS, as commercialization of ideas may be devolved to other organisations. IP market activities may provide an incentive for investment in new knowledge creation but can also lead to opportunistic behaviour. In recent years, some observers have raised concerns regarding a decline in patent quality owing notably to lower legal standards of novelty and to the work overload of examiners in patent offices, globally. It should be noted that the WP9.2 Innovation Survey showed a slight increase in patents at pending and application stage, although only 1-2 had been sold.

5. **Markets and competition** - markets for intermediate and final products and services are equally critical for innovation. Competition fosters innovation by giving bodies incentives to innovate in order to be more effective and to survive. However, if competition does not allow innovators to recover the costs of their investments in innovation, the rate of those investments can decline. This is where the relationship with Industry as a supplier and user need to be clarified to entice industry collaboration for research excellence, without direct competition to end results.
6. **Standards** – they can also significantly affect innovation by facilitating the interoperability necessary for competition and setting common ground rules, terminology, and measurement techniques that facilitate the diffusion of innovation. This is most applicable to digital standardization of, for example, metadata for ARCHLAB and DIGILAB by diffusing standards across E-RIHS users and their organisations.
7. **Policy framework** – policy rationales, objectives, and instruments define the nature of public intervention in support of innovation. For example, H2020 targeting societal challenges through research funding has re-routed where innovation is made under thematic goals. The larger number of policy instruments used, the greater variety of objectives pursued, and the wider number of actors involved in innovation policy have increased the complexity of its policy landscape and enhanced risks of inconsistencies and redundancies between policies and programs. Seeking coherence and balance in the set of policies that affect innovative entrepreneurship, co-ordinating with the actors involved in these policies, measuring and evaluating policies consequently have become increasingly important issues. This is an area of risk, unless addressed for E-RIHS.
8. **Geo-political culture** - where you were born, where you live, the language you speak, where you work, how you were educated and the culture of those elements all contribute to how and who you co-create with. Different languages and communication barriers, cultural viewpoints, perceived threats, contribute to what are seen as potential innovation priorities. Every culture, every education system and every advanced community of research has strengths and weakness. Being aware of the weak links and how the geo-political climate will favour innovation is a step in the right direction. Some countries have agendas for jobs creation and innovation investment as a part of economic recovery. Some may favour R&D investment in heritage science as cultivating a ‘soft’ diplomacy tool between countries or regions. Politically, culture can be weaponized and used to advantage in times of change to reassure citizens.

Inhibitors

Most organisations are averse to **risk** of any kind. The amount of risk involved will be a factor in decision-making for future developments. Interestingly, the US have a different attitude to **trial and error** in venturing into unknown territories. Failure, and learning from it, is seen to drive innovation³³. There is an Affordable Loss principle where the risk of failure outweighs the potential gain. This support for failure has been suggested as a future consideration for innovation in the EU.

Lack of uniformity – legal and otherwise- across the national borders of member states can be obstructive to innovation. This is of particular note for a distributed infrastructure such as E-RIHS. Uniformity on topics such as data retention, cloud computing, baseline integrity such as isotopic analysis is an issue which can inhibit new departures, but should be treated as an opportunity for E-RIHS to lead the way as an open cloud ERIC and for excellence in heritage standards, with knowledge spillover to other disciplines allowing inter-operability across systems and best practice applications.

Analysis of overlaps between the WP9.2 Innovation Survey and the WP9 ERIC National Contact Points surveys gave more specific insights. A list of ten common obstacles were ranked in each survey. The strongest obstacles shared between each survey as:

- a. a lack of organizational/ national supports
- b. an over-emphasis on short-term/ personal objectives at an organizational and national level.

In the ERIC's National Contact Points Survey, respondents had a more over-arching view of the research landscape, these are priority issues to address when looking at ERIHS as an innovation eco-system.

Interestingly, felt to be of least obstruction to innovation by the WP9.2 Innovation Survey respondents from the Heritage Science community were:

- poor external communication
- poor external communication
- lack of an innovation monitoring system.

In contrast, NCP's felt that all of the above were some of the most important inhibitors. It may be that the NCP's are indicating the priorities for collaboration, communication and systemic innovation systems trickling down from policy agendas. Whereas, HS User communities are being asked increasingly to focus on Innovation and see it as an unknown realm in which they would like to be upskilled to respond to organizational agendas. It may be of use to monitor these inhibitor rankings between the two groups over the next five years, as E-RIHS transitions from construction to operation within the FP9 landscape.

Rank	Heritage Science Advanced Community	ERIC National Contact Points
1	Lack of Organisational/ National Supports	Lack of Organisational/ National Supports
2	Lack of Funding	Poor External Communication
3	Focus on Short-term/ Personal Objectives	Lack of Collaboration
4	Poor Training in Innovation	Absence of Innovation Monitoring Systems
5	Lack of Time for Innovative Thinking	Focus on Short-term/ Personal Objectives
6	Lack of Access to Innovation Implementation	Lack of Funding
7	Lack of Collaboration	Lack of Time for Innovative Thinking
8	Poor Internal Communication	Lack of Access to Innovation Implementation
9	Absence of Innovation Monitoring System	Poor Internal Communication
10	Poor External Communication	Poor Training in Innovation

Table ranking the main inhibitors to innovation - Overlaps between Heritage Science Community and ERIC NCP's

6. ACTORS IN HERITAGE SCIENCE INNOVATION

An innovative approach in itself, E-RIHS is expected to generate more opportunities for innovation by exploiting the prolific interaction between providers and users building also strong links with industrial partners and the broader heritage industry. Most of the innovations developed so far in the E-RIHS organizations, as recorded by the E-RIHS PP-9.2 Innovation Survey (see Section 7), fall under the Use-led and Research-based Innovation cases, even though occasionally Technology transfer and Spill-overs have been achieved. These can certainly be further enhanced given the present experience as outlined in Section 4 (Directions for E-RIHS Innovations), other areas can be enabled including, for example, non-economic, non-technological and social innovations.

To ensure the E-RIHS innovation ecosystem (see Fig. 8) is exploited in a balanced way, the role of the main players in the RI framework, namely the access providers, the users and the broader heritage industry needs to be carefully analysed with respect to the individual and more importantly the combined contributions of these actors to developing innovation.

The role of providers - laboratories, research centres and clusters

By their definition and mission RIs represent unique facilities, tools, resources and expertise, enabling cutting-edge research. For achieving, maintaining and extending these features of uniqueness, access providers are naturally and constantly in the hunt of innovation. In RIs, there exists a distinct advantage considering that researchers in these facilities are not isolated in terms of their range of activities. Hence they benefit from continuous interaction with colleagues in “neighboring” facilities or even competing ones on a push-pull basis. Scientists at RIs interact strongly with users and other innovators (e.g. equipment industry) fostering the potential for generating novel tools, methods and approaches for conducting top-level research.

- Development of new work stations (e.g. beamlines) or instruments (e.g. portable, hybrid instruments).
- Development of efficient methodologies and protocols for performing measurements.
- Development of new methods for collecting, processing and analyzing data (e.g. advanced imaging, data fusion).
- Adopting tools (equipment, methods) from other science and engineering sectors (e.g. use of biomedical imaging or diagnostic tools, or non-destructive testing methods from engineering or industrial contexts).
- Developing efficient ways to provide access to large and diverse types of data and information
- Extending tools and methods for efficient data use, interpretation, re-use and management.

A major impact of RIs that one should not overlook, and is indirectly but strongly linked to innovation, relates to the development of new skills that improve significantly the capacities and qualities of scientists, including early-stage researchers (see also E-RIHS PP, D7.1). This capacity building enhances job opportunities either within the RI sector or beyond the latter generating important diffusion of skills, capabilities and innovation to other sectors.

Fig. 8: Graphical representation of the Innovation Ecosystem and the interplay of actors in HS innovation

The role of users in innovation development, use and exploitation

New user communities are growing and the role of the user in HS RI's is constantly evolving. The Advanced Community of Heritage Science users convey high level of interdisciplinary knowledge and background data in relation to their specific research subject/project. They formulate detailed, advanced questions to approach and issues to address, in several fields of heritage science. Those fields span archaeology, archaeometry, paleontology, art history and conservation, digital heritage. The WP9 Innovation Survey indicated that the largest respondee by discipline was from chemistry, archaeology, physics and engineering. In the context of that respondee profile, it is encouraging to see that 42.3% of those repondees has written ten or more articles in the cultural heritage field in the last five years. And so we must plan for a wide, and growing, spectrum of users (see Fig. 9).

This type of user-provider interaction can be an enabling one, particularly within a proper innovation ecosystem. It has the potential of generating innovation in co-development of next generation instruments, methods or knowledge management tools for advancing the state of the art across the HS domain. Indeed the user plays a key role in the virtuous circle of innovation³⁴ within the HS-RI environment in several ways by:

- bringing in high quality proposals (evaluated through a peer-review procedure) for performing experiments that often constitute new applications that stimulate innovation;
- assessing the effectiveness of innovative approaches /innovative products and if/where needed offering directions for critical instrumental or methodological improvements;

Fig.9: WP9 Innovation Survey – Number of articles written by respondees in the cultural heritage field in last 5 years

- proposing re-use of the innovation in other applications in several scientific disciplines or where sectors cross together (physics, chemistry, biology, geosciences, energy, cultural heritage, archaeology, etc).

Depending on the user specific discipline and the RI platforms accessed (physical sciences, digital, archives) several cases, which potentially lead to innovation can be identified, in close parallels to those listed above in relation to the access providers, including:

- Technological innovation with respect to specialization/adaptation of equipment for analysis and diagnostics including hybridization of techniques and instruments;
- Methodological innovation concerning the combined use of complementary methodologies enabling holistic approaches to analysis and documentation;
- Methodological innovations by use statistical methods (e.g. chemometrics, neural networks, machine learning) for data processing and analysis;
- Easy, open and enhanced access to data and information;
- Mechanisms and interfaces enabling access to digital archives, semantically linked open data (metadata for linked data sets, good practice);
- Computing facilities and e-services, cloud based services, data mining or other relevant for HS services;
- Assessment and re-use of data in innovative applications;
- Best practice guides for all the above.

Industry in the field of Heritage Science

Industry is considered as a key player in the development and the future of RIs, and according to the INNO WG a “bi-directional” focus is put in all its activities on the improvement of the mutual cooperation between RIs and industry³⁵. In the case of Heritage Science, such a multi-disciplinary domain with a multi-faceted field of applications, “Industry” may be

Image © DARIAH

Case Study 2: DARIAH ERIC Innovation Forum

The DARIAH ERIC Innovation Forum, held in Aarhus as the European Capital of Culture 2017, strengthened and further explored co-operations of DARIAH and traditional industries associated with Arts and Humanities, like design and media, as well as new digital industries, like game development, social media, VR and AR. It brought together researchers and the creative industries. Through its membership organisations, DARIAH already has a large expertise in the management and creative use of complex digital media assets, which underlie a lot of economic activity within the context of the European content industries. This is a good model of the facilitating the User in the cycle of development, use and exploitation.

considered with a wider view as anyone outside of pure academia with revenue/ commercial potential. In general, “application field” might be a better term than “industry” in the common point of view. Considering the industry in a broad sense as revenue-driven commercial companies and/or organisations, museums or galleries can be considered as specific “industries” in the culture heritage field.

Application fields for heritage science in ‘industry’ reach far and wide. The UK SEAHA Centre is a leading academic heritage science centre. Examples of its industry partners range from photonics, laser ablation, architecture, building heritage conservation, 3D imaging, nano-fabrication, computational linguistics, AL developer companies and more. The above are predominantly scientific bodies or companies. SEAHA also works closely with heritage agencies. If heritage is included in the application field for E-RIHS users, then the scope is widened to include art conservation companies, cultural institutions, archaeological societies/companies, underwater heritage organisations, tourism management and others. There is a wide spectrum of what could be classed as industry for heritage science, and therefore, large potential for E-RIHS industry users.

Industry as a user, as a partner or supplier

E-RIHS, as an infrastructure in the young but dynamic field of heritage science, has a large potential of engaging industry. It possesses an excellent pool of novel ideas, which industry can implement, while acting as a reference body for consultation and proof of concepts. The industry users of the E-RIHS infrastructure will be bringing in, due to the complexity and specificity of the Heritage Science, ever more challenging tasks. To address such tasks, new methods and experimental setups will have to be developed. Here, **industry as a supplier** can assist scientists and/or engineers in the construction or upgrade of facilities (design, engineering), with high opportunities for technology transfer, as sources of (pre-)commercial procurements of new high-tech components, instruments and related services. In parallel, **industry as a user** can have access to facilities for industrial research and innovation, offering opportunities to lower or eliminate technological barriers leading to further innovation and to generate knowledge transfer.

Clearly, there are a multitude of ways industry can be involved in innovation produced in RI ecosystems, as cited³³:

- New knowledge production and dissemination: Publications | Access to data and tools for accessing them | Outreach
- Access to infrastructures, including provision of specialised service and expertise: with appropriate access and charging mechanisms
- Training and human resources development: Knowledge Transfer | Staff mobility

- Contribution to economic activities: Design and co-design of instrumentation and equipment, Joint research projects (with dedicated funding and interface), Contract based R&D, including testing (provision of specialist services), Licensing of IP, Spin-off creation, business incubation and acceleration services.

Good cases exist indicating fruitful RI-industry synergies in the field of heritage science, for instance:

- software tools and data processing methods developed as plugins to existing SW solutions for virtual computer generated tomography models that allow thorough investigation of 3D object structures. In cultural heritage, it is often needed to reveal fine details of decoration on corroded or damaged archaeological objects. A specific tool for a sub-sequential erasure of certain areas to visualize the details on curved surfaces would offer great benefit, whereas its implementation is not a highly demanding task.
- the XRF spectrometers, used often for material sorting in industrial environments, after specific modifications and adaptations found their way to the heritage science field. They are used now for non-destructive analyses of historical pigments and some manufacturers are developing instruments optimized for heritage applications.

An important consideration though is that industry, particularly the technology sector, most often needs to obtain results / solutions in a relatively short time frame and under tight deadlines. To accommodate this sort of pressure RIs, would need to make room and, besides their strategic focus on large and challenging projects, allow for targeted smaller scale projects with industrial partners in order to create trustworthy links. Furthermore, in order to communicate effectively with industry, key members of the RI scientists or engineers should be trained appropriately in business skills (WP7) and interact with or even staff their technology transfer unit.

The Commission Staff working document on Long-term sustainability of RIs³¹ states the involvement of industry as an important point that has to be improved in RIs. To facilitate this task, there are several actions that need to be considered in the context of E-RIHS:

- awareness on the RI services and tools (the available services / tools of the RI must be communicated in a general way to the public, with a special accent on the industry. The suitable approach is informing potential industrial partners about the progress by means of newsletters with overviews of possibilities and examples of usage of the RI (WP8.1)
- training of the users (WP7) will contain topics important for the industrial users
- training of the personnel (WP7) with focus on communication skills for industrial involvement
- the access procedures for industry have to be specific (WP5)
- remote control access and virtual use should be promoted where possible
- simplified access rules should be applied for new user groups
- up-to-date Catalogue of Services will be available
- industry- and innovation-friendly data policies should be in place
- IPR policy should be transparent and efficient
- dissemination and stimulation actions should be carried out in close connection with sectorial industrial organisations and with EU support

There is a rather straightforward possibility of cooperation of RIs and industry on novel instrumental solutions and methods. For this, it is important to increase the visibility of the potential cooperation opportunities, target the appropriate industrial partners that are likely to engage with the RIs and share the best practices. Industrial players can also be present in Advisory Boards. Exchange programs and staff mobility with industry can help to increase the cooperation potential.

In conclusion, there is a clear need of mediation to facilitate the technology transfer and industrial support, as discussed in Section 8. The technology transfer offices of E-RIHS should be active in this field. The cooperation with industry, and even the mere access of industry to the RIs, bears an important question concerning intellectual property rights (IPR) (see Industry & ARCHLAB/MOLAB success story (see Case Study 3). To overcome these problems, specific access modes may have to be defined for industry, defining also the handling of results and IPRs. The JRC Framework for Access³⁶ can serve as a good example and base for the E-RIHS specific needs. The WP9.2 Innovation Survey demonstrates that collaboration between heritage science relevant organisations and industry has significant growth potential. 65% of respondents showed that their organizations had none or five, or under, such collaborations over the last five years (see Fig. 10).

Fig.10: Number of Collaborations with Industry by Organisations from the WP9.2 Innovation Survey

Jan van Eyck: Madonna with Canon Joris van der Paele, Groeninge Museum

Case Study 3: Success Story – Industry Collaboration with ARCHLAB & MOLAB

The restoration of the Ghent Altarpiece by Van Eyck (1432) has a long “preparative” history going back to ARCHLAB and MOLAB in 2008-2009. Especially within ARCHLAB, visits to PRADO, National Gallery and C2RMF were fruitful in understanding the conservation state and restoration history of works of Jan van Eyck and followers. It was not only at the basis for the scientific restoration project (2012-2019) but it followed with further projects funded by the Belgian Science Policy, in collaboration with the Getty Foundation, Bruges Musea, University of Brussels and a spin-off company leading finally to the freely accessible scientific imaging data of artworks of Van Eyck present in all precious European Musea available via legacy.closetovaneyck.be website.

7. INNOVATION ANALYSIS FOR E-RIHS LABS

Considering the development of E-RIHS, and its path towards innovation, it is instructive to look into the current situation and assess the existing and the potential for further innovations. In this context, it cannot be underemphasized that along this path, several innovations emerged over the past decade through RI-based projects, supported by the EC, such as EU-Artech, CHARISMA, IPERION-CH, ARIADNE or PARTHENOS.

A general overview would classify these innovations as (see also Section 4):

- Research-based: novel analytical tools based on emerging technologies and cutting-edge engineering that allow to efficiently address or improve the characterization of heritage materials or structures;
- Heritage (Use)-led: new methodologies that enable a global, multi-parameter understanding of heritage objects;
- Knowledge spillover-technology transfer (primarily inward): adaptation of tools and methods from other fields and disciplines such as geosciences (GIS), biology and medicine (genetic methods, imaging), materials science and nanotechnology (new materials for conservation); math and computer science (data handling and processing and data management). However knowledge spillover from HS to external innovation actors should be fostered.
- Access type: novel and efficient modes of access to analytical technologies (FIXLAB, MOLAB), physical archives (ARCHLAB) or online scientific data (DIGILAB) that increase opportunities for exchange, interaction and close cooperation on an interdisciplinary basis among a broad spectrum of providers and user communities;
- Access policy: open data sharing and e-infrastructures³⁷ that ensure sustainable, open digital archives through the development of research e-infrastructure computing facilities and e-services, cloud based services, data mining or other relevant for HS services;

Obviously many more can be developed through E-RIHS, in the future. In fact, this overall positive outlook has sparked great interest towards the creation of key RIs for serving various heritage research communities and this is the reason ESFRI has introduced a number of pan-European RIs in the SSH domain (DARIAH, CLARIN, ESS, SHARE and CESSDA), with E-RIHS being the latest addition in the 2016 Roadmap.

E-RIHS PP 9.2 Innovation Survey – overview of results

The aim of the WP9.2 Innovation Survey was to attempt a mapping of the innovation landscape which several RIs servicing the Heritage Science community (within E-RIHS and beyond) operate in. The results were combined with those of the ERIC's National Contact Points Innovation Survey, which aimed to capture an over-arching view of issues for research infrastructures.

Interestingly, respondents of both the WP9.2 Innovation and the ERIC NCP's Surveys listed the majority of innovations to be new methods or instrumentation, with 'other' largely digital, new materials or process related. Therefore, areas of user

facilitation, data facilitation and knowledge transfer are open to exploitation for innovations. A graphical breakdown of the various areas of innovation is shown in Figure 11. With the exception of knowledge transfer, most of the cases described by the respondents evidently fall under the **research-based** or **use-led innovation**. It should be noted that even though the survey may not have exhaustively traced all the innovation cases, it does, however, provide an overall quite informative snapshot.³⁸ The list of innovations, as presented by the responders, is given in the following section organized according to the typologies indicated in Figure 10.

Fig.11: Innovation Survey results on most common areas where innovations are made

An important aspect of innovation is the impact it has on the RI operation. It is clearly recognized by the respondents (Q10: *Please rank in importance the main impact of the cases of innovation outcomes*) that their innovation has very significant impact in the quality of access/service provided. In almost all cases both potential application scenarios for and user communities interested in the innovation are from within the HS field.

It is also noteworthy (Q13: *Please estimate, in the last 5 years, the number of patents from your organisation (or department of) relevant to cultural heritage*) that non-negligible, yet weak impact is seen towards economic exploitation as traced by positive responses for licensing, patents or setting up spin-off companies (for the last 5 years).

Innovation Cases

The following tables collect input from the respondents concerning innovative cases developed in their organization, separated in the different typologies shown in table below.

New methodologies

Imaging, tomography, microscopy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of 3D hyperspectral imaging • Enhanced visualization of near infrared reflectograms • Development of infrared spectroscopic mapping tomography • Development of acoustic microtomography for non-invasive documentation of heritage objects. Application to detect glaze delamination in heritage tiles. • Development of spectracoustic tomography (combined ultrasonics and spectroscopic tomographic techniques) • Nonlinear optical microscopy (NLM) modalities of Multi- Photon Excited Fluorescence (MPEF) for the nondestructive accurate determination of the chemical nature, structure and thickness within multi-layered samples • New methodology for making digital color reconstructions • Methodological approaches and pioneer applications of neutron techniques in different industrial and CH sectors, Use of neutron diffraction and imaging to non-destructively characterize historical metal artifacts • Applying the CT-Tomography to historic objects
Spectrochemical and other chemical / chemometrics / analytical methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantification approach adapted for portable/handheld XRF spectrometers, e.g. in micro-XRF analysis with polycapillary optics. • Development of angular resolved XRF analysis for chemical speciation and trace element analysis of decorated ceramics, • Combining PIXE/XRF with GRT for non-destructive bulk analysis • THz spectroscopy • Laser based techniques for analysis and processing of cultural heritage objects • Specific instrument LA-ICP/MS; Treatments for degraded manuscripts; Dating and analysis of metallic sculptures • Combined use of isotopic and molecular mass spectrometry for archaeozoology • New technology on optical pH chemical sensors to evaluate the environmental acidity, in air or other media. • New method of sampling of ink from letters and drawings • New methodology for identification of plastics • 1st application of ancient genomics in Ireland; development of petrosal bone sampling as the best source of preserved a-DNA • Applying the Tomography to historic objects
Objects curation in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of LED lighting for museums • New standards for showcase performance • New approach to collection management, development of decision making for collection mana

Conservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of consolidation treatments for stone and earthen structures • Green materials for conservation, diagnosis of metals using non-invasive techniques, new methods for conservation of metals • New laser cleaning methodologies, Use of a carbon dioxide laser to re-glaze heritage tiles • Conservation and consolidation through gamma irradiation • Development of ecotoxic coating for the protection of outdoor bronze sculpture
Preventive Conservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of new methodologies for assessing the risk of object damage from internal climates • Development of new ways of monitoring the museum environment • Development of new treatments for museum objects (eg adhesives used in textiles conservation but there are many others)
Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing of electrical resistivity tomography geophysical data, adaptation of methodologies for shallow underwater geophysical prospection, WEB_GIS modelling • Cluster analysis; supervised classification • Key Enabling Technologies (KET) providing a range of products • Development of a Virtual Resaerch Environment (VRE) with reusable workflows and services with the posability to chain processes • Development of resaerch focused alorithms • Adoption of new digital tools which can enhance critical thinking and analysis • Development protocols enabling researchers to document methodologies

NLO microscopy used for assessing structural and photochemical modifications fin the process of laser removal of dammar varnish on paint mock-up sample.

Case Study 4: NLO Microscopy

Research from the bio-medical field is enabling innovation in HS

The application of non-linear optical (NLO) microscopy is gaining ground in the HS research. Introduced initially, early 1990’s, in the field of biological microscopy as a means to achieve high imaging quality in scattering environments, such as cells and tissues, NLO microscopy soon reached the market, while in parallel remained in the focus of further scientific innovations; a highlight has been the Nobel Prize in Chemistry, 2014 (awarded to E. Betzig, S. W. Hell and W. E. Moerner “for the development of super-resolved fluorescence microscopy”).

Recent findings (including research performed in the IPERION CH project) show a promising innovation potential, concerning the application of various types of NLO microscopy (3D- or polarization sensitive imaging) contributing to the study of heritage materials.

New/adapted instrumentation

Laboratory or facility instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific instrument LA-ICP/MS for heritage sample analysis • Development of microfader equipment for nondestructive analysis of light stability of objects • External milli beam PIXE setup for HS applications • Novel X-Ray tomographic device with two perpendicular axes; methods for image processing • Automated illumination dome for RTI/PTM imaging
Spectrochemical and other chemical / chemometrics / analytical methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantification approach adapted for portable/handheld XRF spectrometers, e.g. in micro-XRF analysis with polycapillary optics. • Development of angular resolved XRF analysis for chemical speciation and trace element analysis of decorated ceramics, • Combining PIXE/XRF with GRT for non-destructive bulk analysis • THz spectroscopy • Laser based techniques for analysis and processing of cultural heritage objects • Specific instrument LA-ICP/MS; Treatments for degraded manuscripts; Dating and analysis of metallic sculptures • Combined use of isotopic and molecular mass spectrometry for archaeozoology • New technology on optical pH chemical sensors to evaluate the environmental acidity, in air or other media. • New method of sampling of ink from letters and drawings • New methodology for identification of plastics • 1st application of ancient genomics in Ireland; development of petrosal bone sampling as the best source of preserved a-DNA • Applying the CT-Tomography to historic objects

Knowledge transfer

Teaching, Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research led teaching filters directly into studio practice in conservation of paintings at graduate level education • 1st course on conservation taught and followed from multiple rooms in Continental Portugal and the Azores Islands, to test the concept • Thematic summer workshops on “Optical Technologies in Cultural Heritage – OPTO-CH” • Non-invasive analysis of cultural heritage objects; use of painting materials • Organization of dedicated training courses on XRF techniques and applications in the field of CH Transfer of know-how and expertise to museum professionals to support an effective utilization of portable XRF spectrometers in routine and research work within the museum conservation laboratory environment.
Digital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clustering effect will Interconnect people, data, methods and research centres which will ultimately improve authorship and trust • People involved in day to day research practices will collaborate and contribute to those developing and designing tools • Development of scripting skills within HS community • Enable cross fertilisation and multidisciplinary approaches within E-RIHS but also potnetial to other humanities based ERICs (ESS, DARIAH, CLARIN)

User facilitation / new services

Online access to archaeological
/ scientific data

- Access to facilities and online access to archaeological scientific data at the Hungarian National Museum Laboratory for Applied research.
- One stop platform for a variety of archaeometry services (NIPNE facility, Bucharest)
- Open access to 3D documentation data of architectural heritage assets (<http://ephemera.cyi.ac.cy/>)
- Enabling web access to very high quality 3D models of Irish monuments
- Developing lab in the gallery programmes, where research is carried out within the Science Gallery Space (Science Gallery Dublin)
- Reduce the need for service replication and the effort they require in creation, maintenance and funding

Data recording, processing,
storage & supports

- Open source tools, MeshLab (<http://www.meshlab.net/>), 3DHOP (<http://vcg.isti.cnr.it/3dhop/>) for the documentation of data related to works of art, or publication on the web of data and related information.
- 1st accredited archive for archaeological data in the world (Archaeology Data Service, Department of Archaeology, U. of York, UK)
- Adoption of VITAL data support system (Dublin City archives)
- Provision of long term and medium term infrastructure to manage and access heritage science data
- Creating solutions to issues and problems with data interoperability, data standardisation and data reuse
- Support digital data management in research e.g. long terms preservation, DRM and IPR
- Data provenance supports

8. TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER & EXPLOITATION

The difference between technology transfer and exploitation has been described as the ‘**push**’ versus the ‘**pull**’ approaches to research results and outputs.

	Technology Transfer	Exploitation
Definition	Describing and making available results so that they can be used	Making use of results, for scientific, societal or economic purposes
Potential Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publication Sharing data/ research in online repository Training Workshops/ demonstrations Policy/ roadmap/ strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PhD post Patent, license, spin-off Product/ service Technique Standard Policy change Societal activity Further research

Technology Transfer

A crucial aspect regarding the smooth operation of RIs, which should be considered by E-RIHS, is the definition of clear and concrete rules regarding the technology transfer procedures. Of particular importance is the protection of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) ownership and its exploitation. When analysing the outcomes of the WP9.2 Innovation Survey, plenty of innovation paradigms in the field of heritage science are reported, while little effort is directed towards the protection and exploitation of IPR. This reflects a lack of awareness and knowledge regarding the technology transfer procedures in the field of heritage science. E-RIHS should encourage a culture that supports innovation exploitation and under certain conditions commercialization (but see Section 4). A technology transfer policy is necessary to clarify the relationship between innovation actors – specifically industry – considering the facilitators and inhibitors laid out in Section 5 and discussed below.

The WP9.2 Innovation Survey also shows that there are large opportunities for increasing the transfer and exploitation potential. A third of the facilities do not have a declared innovation strategy and more than a half do not employ staff to facilitate innovation (see Fig. 12). From this we can infer that there are not active Technology Transfer Offices (TTO’s). This is further supported by the fact that more than two thirds of the responders declare that they are not commercializing the innovation.

Fig.12: Innovation Survey findings on Organization support for facilitating innovation (Q15)

Therefore, setting up a framework in order to support the technology transfer process could be implemented either through the creation of a TTO that will serve E-RIHS centrally or via the engagement of the TTOs of the various institutes and organisations that are members of E-RIHS. According to OECD³⁹, TTOs are responsible for the appropriate IPR management, which enables the transformation of innovation into societal benefits. TTOs have significant roles bridging the gap between research and innovation. They work towards:

- establishing collaboration with industry and other stakeholders
- providing information on opportunities for private and/or public funding
- providing support on areas related to entrepreneurship and intellectual property (IP)
- facilitating exploitation of research outcomes via the creation of spin-off and startup companies
- training of the research and scientific community on technology transfer procedures

There are two types of innovation suitable for exploitation and technology transfer foreseen in E-RIHS:

- results of in-house research
- innovation originating during the cooperation with the users of the infrastructure.

In case of results from own in-house research, the matter can be developed by the individual E-RIHS member independently. Innovation originating from cooperation with a user will have to be assessed under the TTO policy whether it will be developed:

- in cooperation
- as the in-house research
- by the user, without involvement of E-RIHS.

For E-RIHS, the first two possibilities may be preferable over the third, from the strategy and sustainability point of view. The third option is highly dependent on the limit of revenue involved for an ERIC. On the other hand, the user, in particular if it is an industrial partner, can substantially help in bringing the innovation into practice. An important question here is the IPR, which may be answered by corresponding contracts. Whatever option is selected, it must be mutually agreed (WP4 – legal) using a bilateral agreement model.

Exploitation

The most common challenges from the wider research infrastructure landscape regarding exploitation are seen to be:

- overlooking commercial opportunities due to lack of commercial awareness
- failing to establish a patent position or establishing a poor patent position
- failing to exemplify the technology
- failing to protect Intellectual property because of lack of funds
- failing to patent or exploit successfully due to lack of resource
- failing to choose the best exploitation strategy due to lack of experience or knowledge in the field
- failing to negotiate the best terms due to a lack of comprehensive industrial contacts.

While the fundamentals of exploitation practice are applicable across most fields, the above are mostly commercially biased. E-RIHS must also consider other areas of exploitation based around non-economic, technological, non-technological and social exploitation.

The most probable exploitation paths are foreseen as:

- open access: especially in the case of in-house research, some results can be made freely available for those who can exploit them. This approach can be interesting from the point of view of promoting the E-RIHS infrastructure.
- user adoption: third case mentioned above (user takes up the innovation in its own use)
- licensing: commercial terms are agreed between E-RIHS and other organizations to prepare the product / service for the market use (WP4 – legal work)
- spin-out: there is a possibility of establishing companies to supply the products / services.

A significant problem in regard to exploitation is caused by different procedures, possibilities and rules in member countries. Therefore, it may not be reasonable to try to strictly unify the activities of the TTOs across the E-RIHS national nodes. TTOs can only be expected to advise and incentivize Innovation Actors in adherence to best practice and standardization through the exploitation of innovations made. A central E-RIHS TTO would gather this information and support any user or national node TTO's. E-RIHS TTO should also work on increasing the exploitation and technology transfer between the partners with focused trainings and by distributing the best-practice stories. A good example to inspire such an E-RIHS TTO model can be seen under the ENEA project which supports technological transfer and exploitation, can be found in this link⁴⁰.

E-RIHS TTO units focus on active and flexible technology transfer and exploitation, surmounting the common exploitation challenges from inception. The TTOs should also help the researchers to identify research which has a potential commercial interest and results that are worth of patenting.

Case Study 5: University of Malaga: Technology Transfer & Exploitation

The University of Malaga offers the possibility to perform detailed archaeometric analyses on archaeological and cultural heritage objects and samples using different technical instruments. The experimental data can be adequately interpreted with the help of, either, specialized technicians and/or investigators or professors. Once a proper bilateral agreement has been put in place via Knowledge and Research Transfer Office of Malaga University, the outcomes range from publications in scientific journals to performing joint research projects with other institutions or private users.

9. ANALYSIS OF MANAGEMENT & IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURES

Approaches

There are two approaches taken to management of innovation:

1. **Organic** – reacting to enable applications of invention. Incubation can be far more informal with knowledge exchange happening over coffee, at conferences, connecting dots through traditional knowledge exchange etc.
2. **Systemic** or induced – laying a path for innovation with dedicated resources to nurture:
 - A - the ‘invention’ stage via discussion forums
 - B - the application of invention
 - C – anticipate innovation gaps and priorities

It was recommended in the report on Long-term Sustainability for RI’s that a more systemic approach be taken and that specific personnel take on roles supporting the innovation chain, rather than on the project basis which currently predominates amongst RI’s. Once there is an internal infrastructure in place for E-RIHS, connections can be made externally.

The flaw with planning ahead, once processes are established for innovation, is that they become inflexible and only able to respond to what are termed as ‘known knowns’ in security and business management risk assessment. It is said that planning is always outdated in the innovation sector. So how do you create a systemic innovation without inhibiting innovation itself? Systemic innovation is the art of knowing the unknown. And to this end management must be fluid and flexible.

Image © Marmall4

Case Study 6: Mercurial Model for Innovation Management Resourcing on the Go:

- Designate a role, or team, to coordinate the innovation chain process
- Create a preliminary plan for good practices
- Allow for regular – and extraordinary – change to the innovation plan in response to ideas developing
- Enable constant adaptation to new landscapes
- Do not let regulations, risks and other inhibitors prevent ideas developing until the idea is concrete
- Create incentives for innovation
- Create platforms for implementing ‘servitisation’⁴¹, or user driven changes, with rewards for high-input users whose feedback lead to innovations
- Monitor trial and errors, and successes using innovation discovery techniques such as networking and face-to-face communication, along with regular KPI feedback

Mercurial Model for Innovation Management

Implementation of the Mercurial Model (see Case Study 6) will need to work from the core E-RIHS infrastructure. For example, it may be steered by an Activity Director role from E-RIHS centrally. Some multi-use systems can then be developed in line with other WP's, such as taking information from the user communities, E-RIHS Academy and Scholar supports to gain feedback from users in creating or focusing areas for innovation. A key tool in implementation is continuous monitoring through Key Performance indicators (KPI's) which will also contribute to the E-RIHS brand of excellence in science.

Innovation dissemination, societal impact and public engagement

Cultural heritage has a major contribution towards the socio-economic development. Innovation actions emerging from cultural heritage research are found to have a direct impact on numerous societal and economical aspects such as job creation, poverty reduction, new company creation, contribution towards the new economy of knowledge and subsequently regional and national growth. Cultural heritage contributes to the formation of the social capital and enhancement of cohesion and integration as mentioned by the *'Cultural Heritage Counts for Europe'* Report. RIs, in particular, as innovation generators in the cultural heritage domain are acting as enablers for socio-economic development at regional, national and pan-European level.

User communities, such as Heritage scientists in archaeological Institutions or services, museums, galleries, libraries, archives can play a liaison role in the dissemination of research and innovation in the field of Heritage Science, introducing Innovation products or results of innovative approaches for the understanding of heritage in publicly accessed exhibitions/media/digital repositories/e-platforms related to heritage collections, museums, galleries, etc. (see Case Study 7).

Case Study 7: Laser rejuvenation of Caryatids opens to the public at the Acropolis Museum: A link between ancient and modern Greece

The IIC Keck Award 2012 was given out jointly to the Aropolis Museum and IESL-FORTH For their contribution:

“towards the promotion of public understanding and appreciation of the accomplishments of the conservation profession”

The sculpture surface cleaning is achieved by use of a custom design, innovative laser system developed at IESL-FORTH, Greece⁴².

Key Performance Indicators

Rationale for Development of KPIs

Key performance indicators (KPIs) are critical to ensuring that any research processes, methods and products are successful and the data is available to identify and sustain improvements. With KPIs, we are able to evaluate the success of component or facets of the research infrastructure against its established goals. KPI's ensure the mercurial adaptability that is necessary for successful innovation management.

The KPIs developed for E-RIHS have been separated into three distinct groupings which take into considerations the input, throughput and output of the research process. These are:

- Input KPI - Measure of the investment in innovation within Universities and Research Institutes, which carry out Heritage Science (HS). Indicate the level of financial and structural support each Research Institute/ University
- Ongoing Continual KPI – Measure of the throughput of innovation within Universities and Research Institutes, which carry out Heritage Science (HS) an indication of the day-to-day practice of innovation. Could be tracked on a more regular basis.
- Output KPI - Measure of the output of Innovation within Universities and Research Institutes which carry out Heritage Science (HS) a true indicator of the innovation created and developed by an organisation.

In an effort to differentiate between the difference value each KPI has in reflecting innovation, each KPI has been designated a different weighting based upon the relative value with respect to innovation. Gold quality KPIs having the greatest significance, silver less so and bronze the least significance when evaluating their relative innovation.

By analysing the relative Values of these three KPI types against each other we can identify and develop models of innovation which exists and where exemplary and efficient modes innovation exists.

Input KPIs	Continual KPIs	Output KPI	Innovation Scenario
High	High	High	ROI in Innovation identified as expected. Innovation results in-line with initial expectations for Research Institute which receives high levels of investment
High	Moderate	Low	ROI in innovation not being fully realised with the products of innovation being stifled and not realising the full innovation potential. Innovation results are therefore short of high level of initial investment
Low	Moderate	Moderate	ROI in Innovation identified as slightly better than expected. Innovation results in-line with initial expectations for Research Institute which receives low levels of investment
Low	High	High	ROI in innovation identified as much greater than the initial low level of investment, highlighting research institute which provides the environment to nurture and grow innovation with a relatively lower level of investment.

Fig.13: Graphical representation of efficiency of different innovation systems/environments

By using the above criteria, exemplar institutes can be identified, and subsequent analysis carried out to identify what are predominant characteristics and environment, which enable innovation to grow in such a way. In turn for those underperforming institutes, analysis may identify where constriction of the innovative process is taking place and remedies to rectify the issues sought.

Input KPIs

	KPI	Qualitative Measurement	Rating
Research Funding	International funding	Research funds obtained from international agencies and partnership contracts within HS	Gold
	Institutional funding	Public funds allocated for research, percent budget allocated to the University/Research Institute by the government within HS	Silver
	Contractual funding	Funds obtained from contracts, private sector, national agencies, scientific chairs and endowment	Silver
	Grants for collaborative R&D	Competitive research and development and partner matching grants (the former aiming at near-to-market technology generation and the latter promoting research partnerships) for the development of novel products or services, e.g. Innovation vouchers	Bronze
Infrastructure	Centres of excellence in research stimulating creative and efficient research and training environments	Number of highly specialized research centres within University/ Research Institute within the HS domain	Gold
	Laboratories	Number of specialised and central laboratories matching the needs of HS programs and researchers	Silver
	Equipment	Number of specialised instruments/equipment needed for HS research programs	Silver
	Cluster policies	Pooling of physical, human and financial resources for innovation infrastructure and knowledge-based investments knowledge spill-overs among actors in clusters	Silver
	Research material & supplies	Amount of laboratory material and chemicals required for HS research programs	Bronze
Facilities	Computer and networking facilities	Availability of computers, telecommunication and network system within University/Research Institute, e.g. High power computing centres	Silver
	Applications & data bases	Number of electronic applications for research analysis and scientific databases within the HS domain	Silver
Human Resources	Technicians & assistance staff	Number of Technical, non-technical and administrative personnel supporting HS research	Silver
	Researchers	Number of PhD holders, faculty members and researchers participating in HS research	Silver
	Postgraduates	Number of Master and Doctorate students participating in HS research	Bronze

Ongoing Continual KPIs

	KPI	Qualitative Measurement	Rating
Research Programmes	Private sector collaborative contracts	Research and development programs and contracts established with private sector	Silver
	International partnership contracts	International research collaborations and partnership agreements	Gold
	Planned Research Programmes	Research programs corresponding to the strategic plan of the University/Research Institute	Silver
Ongoing Thesis	Master's thesis	Research programs attributed to Master thesis within HS domain	Bronze
	PhD thesis	Research programs attributed to PhD thesis within HS domain	Silver
Conferences Workshops	National Conferences & workshops	Number of participants presenting papers/round tables at national conferences and workshops	Bronze
	International Conferences & workshops	Number of participants presenting papers/round tables at International Conferences & workshops	Gold
Training	Training of Researchers	Continuous training programs of researchers in technical methodologies and scientific research management	Silver
	Training of technical staff	Continuous training of technical staff in scientific research	Bronze
Facility Monitoring	Internal institution availability of service	Time facilities are available for use within Research Institute/University	Bronze
	Internal cross domain institution availability of service	Time facilities are available for use within Research Institute/University across disciplines	Silver
	National institution availability of service	Time facilities are available for use Outside Research Institute/ University nationally	Silver
	International institution availability of service	Time facilities are available for use Outside Research Institute/ University internationally	Gold
	Efficiency of provided service	Percentage of service requests resolved within an agreed-on period of time	N/A
	Service Level Monitoring	Number of completed/outstanding actions since SLA review	N/A
	Availability of service	Overall accessibility to service	N/A

Output KPIs

	KPI	Qualitative Measurement	Rating
Publications	Citations	The number of scientists citing published paper as reference in their research papers	Silver
	Publications in SJR journals	Scientific papers published in ISI journals classified according the journal IF value (list to be defined) e.g. CiteScore	Silver
	Publications in non-classified journals	Scientific papers published in ISI and non-ISI journal (list to be defined)	Bronze
	Publications in Nature & Science	Scientific papers published in Nature and Science journals	Gold
	Authored books & chapters	Scientific books written, edited and chapters authored by one or more University/Research Institute Members	Silver
	Translated books & chapters	Scientific books translated by one or more faculty members	Silver
	Data citations	The number of scientists citing published scientific datasets	Silver
Awarded Thesis	Awarded Master thesis	Master of Science (MSc) degrees awarded domain	Bronze
	Awarded PhD thesis	Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degrees awarded in HS domain	Silver
Patents	Patents registered in USA, Europe, Japan	Patents achieved and registered in USA, Europe, Japan	Silver
	Patents registered in other countries	Patents achieved and registered in any other country	Gold
Research & Industry Exchange	Shared conferences & workshops participation	Number of shared publications, conferences and workshops between University/Research Institute and Industry	Bronze
Financial ROI	Revenue from local research	Value of funds gained from research & development in HS at the national level	Silver
	Revenue from external research	Value of funds gained from research & development in HS at the international level	Silver
Societal Outreach	Press/Magazines	Number articles in major newspapers/popular magazines which demonstrate HS R&S to public	Silver
	TV/Radio	Number TV/Radio documentary/features which demonstrate HS R&S to public	Gold
	Exhibitions	Number of exhibitions or displays which demonstrate HS R&S to public	Gold

Output KPIs

	KPI	Qualitative Measurement	Rating
Technology Transfer & Commercialization (TTC) with Industry	Training and education	Number of formal training programs developed between a company and an academic institution/Research Institute	Silver
	Hiring students and researchers from universities/research centres	Number of researchers and technical staff who	Silver
	Sharing of equipment, instruments and technology services with Industry	Access to University/Research Institute R&D facilities by Industrial partners	Gold
	Sharing of equipment, instruments and technology services with University/Research Institute	Access to Industrial partners IR&D facilities by University/Research Institute	Gold
	Industrial prototypes	Innovative industrial and functional prototype achieved by the research team	Gold
	Transferral of models	Re-processing of an imported material, apparatus or device to improve service/analysis.	Gold
	Knowledge Transfer Partnerships	MOU signed between University /Research Institute with Industrial partner	Silver
	Selling/licensing of intellectual property	Number of license agreements between University /Research Institute with Industrial partner	Gold
	Contracting of technology services and intellectual assets	Number of technical consultancies provided by University / Research Institute	Silver
	Sponsored research and R&D collaboration	Number of industrially sponsored/funded research projects	Gold

Qualitative Societal KPIs

Even though the main focus on the innovation indicator metrics presented can be measured with quantitative statistics on research activities and outputs, societal benefits of E-RIHS and its associated innovations must be measured and recorded. These will often take the form of an overall increased understanding, recognition and protection of our cultural heritage assets amongst the general population. However it is difficult to attribute these down stream benefits directly to E-RIHS and heritage science activities. Effort must therefore be made to track and record the propagation of these benefits within the wider community through a series of qualitative observations and ensure that E-RIHS activities are communicated effectively to the general public and those within the cultural heritage sector who primary responsibility is outreach and engagement.

10. KEY FINDINGS

- The EU policy and funding landscape into which E-RIHS will be born is prime for E-RIHS, as both are to have a high innovation focus. Thematic strands of policy and supports will also support multi-disciplinarity – a unique selling point of E-RIHS
- Smart specialisation approaches favoured by EU and national research agendas, may be excluding to a heritage science RI. To benefit, E-RIHS will have to align itself to more ICT and science aspects of innovation developments
- National funding is key to all levels of E-RIHS – state membership fees and national coordination roles, for example. Therefore, innovation are a crucial argument to rely on in justifying state membership.
- A focus on economic innovations for industry partnership is not sustainable to the future of E-RIHS
- Focusing on non-economic, technological, non-technological and social innovations are seen as priority for all four LABS
- Relevant innovation facilitators – curiosity, skills, IPR, geo-political culture - and inhibitors – lack of uniformity, risk aversion - should be addressed at E-RIHS construction phase for a sustainable future
- Using aspects of E-RIHS LABS for public education/ training resources should be considered
- The HS User community is diverse and growing. Increasing industry collaborations, indications of patent growth and surprising numbers of publications in the cultural heritage filed within the last 5 years from the chemistry, physics, archaeology and conservation science fields suggest a community which is prime for future innovations
- The HS User community and the RI National Contact Points differ on what are the priority inhibitors for innovation
- The HS definition of ‘industry’ may be innovative in itself. Cultural institutions, as just one element of that industry, are atypical to RI’s industry partnerships. It can provide a bridge for heritage organisations to Open Innovation supports, along with skills, services, career development areas

- While new techniques and new, or refined, instrumentation are the most common innovations made, knowledge transfer and user facilitation have unfulfilled needs that may be exploited for innovation
- In the majority of respondents, areas of innovation of relevance to MO/ FIX/ ARCHLABS, as the survey was circulated to experts within IPERION CH, amongst others. DIGILAB was addressed by a smaller number. However, data management, supports and e-infrastructures are a pressing concern and, potentially, the area for largest innovation under DIGILAB
- It is evident from surveys where the key areas of innovation have been, and can be, made – see Section 7. From analysis and discussions, it was also evident that there was very little systematic discussion on future innovations. E-RIHS can build on this unfulfilled need
- Systemic innovation infrastructure across the E-RIHS innovation chain are favoured, over project-based innovation supports
- Technology transfer and exploitation are visualised as the ‘push’ versus the ‘pull’ approaches to research results and outputs. The economic limitations on E-RIHS exploitation of knowledge assets, addressed in the governance, legal and financial WP’s, indicate that E-RIHS should direct its infrastructure towards technology transfer outputs and devolve exploitation outputs to a national or industry level
- Successful management of innovation depends on a mercurial approach. A skeleton of supports must allow for constant adaptation to new innovations
- To do so, a series of KPI’s has been constructed as an innovation monitoring tool. It is important to factor in qualitative measures also, as the impacts of heritage science innovations cannot be wholly assessed by quantitative indicators

11. METHODOLOGY

'Innovation' is a term that is used extensively and can have multi-faceted meanings. To address innovation for E-RIHS, both oversight of and insight into the innovation landscape where E-RIHS would be born was deemed crucial. The WP team took a macro to micro approach. The design of the research methodology centred around a chain of investigation, starting with the academic concept development of innovation, honing in on innovation in the current heritage science landscape.

Considering the diverse applications surrounding innovation, together with the four E-RIHS LABS and the multi-disciplinarity of E-RIHS itself, triangulation of quantitative and qualitative research was used.

Step 1:

The first research step was to develop an in-depth understanding of the core concepts to innovation, within the context of the economic, scientific and commercial worlds through extensive academic research using all resources available to the WP team.

Step 2:

The second step was to analysis the policy, strategy and funding context around innovation. Policies from research relevant and specific innovation spheres on national, EU and international levels were analysed. The objective was to:

- understand agendas and supports available for innovation in the current research landscape
- identify relevant issues to be addressed for the construction and operational phases of E-RIHS
- identify areas for exploitation.

These two steps gave a context of understanding and a filter for pertinent issues for Steps 3 & 4.

Step 3:

Two surveys were designed using the Survey Monkey platform:

1. WP9.2 NCP ERIC's Innovation Survey (Annex 1)
2. WP9.2 Innovation Survey (Annex 2)

The surveys were designed overlap in areas, to corroborate results and highlight inconsistencies from the different points of view.

The WP9.2 NCP ERIC's Innovation Survey aimed to capture an over-arching view of issues for research infrastructures. To do so, all listed National Contact Points in the EU and Associated Countries were contacted to garner their insights on innovation patterns in RI's. The survey was directly distributed by using the NCP contact database, publicly available on RICH 2020⁴³. There were 14 respondents. The questions were planned to:

- profile each respondent NCP country and the ERIC's they were responsible for
- capture patterns on innovation typologies, impact, visibility, dissemination, enablers and inhibitors.

Case studies of best practice were requested for innovation types, particularly non-economic instances.

The WP9.2 Innovation Survey aimed to capture more insight to cases of innovation and issues, specifically for heritage science. To do so, the advanced community of heritage science was targeted – from research and cultural institutions to scientific facilities and facilitators of innovation. The survey was circulated internally to the E-RIHS participants and the IPERION CH project contacts, to focus on MOLAB, FIXLAB and ARCHLAB's future in E-RIHS. Each WP Team Member also targeted ten relevant people within their own research environment or country who were potential valuable contributors. There were 100 respondents. The questions were planned to:

- profile each respondent's relationship within the heritage science community
- capture patterns on innovation typologies, impact, visibility, dissemination, enablers and inhibitors
- identify funding sources, commercial activity and systemic innovation engagement
- highlighting unfulfilled gaps for innovation in heritage science

Case studies of best practice in heritage science innovation were requested.

* Please note that the survey data is available to the E-RIHS participants, and on request to the public in D4Science.

Step 4:

Qualitative data was conducted following the first two steps and as the results of the surveys prompted successful instances of innovation and common issues. All respondents to the two surveys were notified that an interview may follow. A list of Expert Interviews conducted can be viewed in Annex 3. The Project Coordinators of the MO/ FIX/ ARCHLAB's were contacted to discuss how the LABS should transition into E-RIHS and where innovations could be made regarding operational aspects. Other experts were:

- new to, or interested in becoming part of, the heritage science community
- had experience in innovation practice

The interviews were done either fact-to-face or via Skype. A template was used for all interviews, focusing on identifying potential typologies of innovations or unfulfilled needs, for ease of data collation.

12. REFERENCES

- 1 <http://www.e-rihs.eu/>
- 2 E-RIHS flyerXXXXXXXX
- 3 E-RIHS overview for SABXXX
- 4 <http://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/E-RIHS-in-one-page-2017.10.02.pdf>
- 5 ESFRI Recommendation on E-RIHS Proposal for 2016 ESFRI Roadmap
- 6 D9.1 First version of the E-RIHS Scientific Vision XXXXXX
- 7 Oslo Manual: Guidelines for Collecting and Interpreting Innovation Data XXXXX
- 8 Innovation Scoreboard 2014 XXXXX
- 9 Schumpeter, J. A. (2014) [1942]. *Capitalism, socialism and democracy* (2nd ed.). Floyd, Virginia: Impact Books. ISBN 978-1617208652.
- 10 Kline, S.J. (1985). *Research, Invention, Innovation and Production: Models and Reality*, Report INN-1, March 1985, Mechanical Engineering Department, Stanford University.
- 11 *Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World – A vision for Europe*, EC, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2016; doi:10.2777/061652
- 12 Chesbrough, H. W. (2003), *The Era of Open Innovation*, MIT Sloan Management Review, Spring 2003: 35-41
- 13 Henderson R.M. and Clark K.B. (1990) *Architectural Innovation: The Reconfiguration of Existing Product Technologies and the Failure of Established Firms*, in *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 35, No. 1, Special Issue: Technology, Organizations, and Innovation (Mar., 1990), pp. 9-30.
- 14 Hansen M.T., Birkinshaw J. (2007) *The Innovation Chain*. *Harv Bus Rev.* 2007 Jun;85(6):121-30, 142.PMID: 17580654
- 15 *Blueprint, High Level group on Innovation Policy Management*, <https://www.highlevelgroup.eu/innovation-policy-management>
- 16 *Leveraging The Innovation Ecosystem for Business Advantage: A Cross-Border Study*, <http://www.technopolis-group.com/report/leveraging-innovation-ecosystem-business-advantage-cross-border-study/>
- 17 https://www.jef.or.jp/journal/pdf/169th_cover02.pdf
- 18 <https://www.globalinnovationindex.org>
- 19 [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2017/608697/EPRS_IDA\(2017\)608697_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2017/608697/EPRS_IDA(2017)608697_EN.pdf)
- 20 https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-proposals-research-innovation-may2018_en.pdf
- 21 <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/open-innovation-open-science-open-world-vision-europe>
- 22 <http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/home>
- 23 <https://dbe.gov.ie/en/Publications/Publication-files/Research-Priority-Areas-2018-to-2023.pdf>

- 24 <http://www.esfri.eu/ri-world-news/staff-working-document-long-term-sustainability-research-infrastructures>
- 25 https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/pdf/esfri/publications/esfri_scripta_vol2.pdf
- 26 <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/1dd62bd1-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1>
- 27 <http://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>
- 28 http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_gii_2017-chapter1.pdf
- 29 Report 2015 EAG Research Infrastructures Including e-Infrastructures
- 30 “Big Science and Innovation”, Simmonds, P. et al (2013)
- 31 https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/pdf/swd-infrastructures_323-2017.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none
- 32 https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/pdf/eric_en.pdf
- 33 Mendoza, S. (2014), Actions for a Sustainable and Competitive Open Innovation Ecosystem in the EU from a US Perspective, European Commission, ISBN: 978-92-79-36414-3, doi: 10.2759/42917.
- 34 ESFRI Roadmap 2016 – Working Group on Innovation, Report to ESFRI – March 2016 <https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/?pg=library&cat=esfri> (accessed February 2018)
- 35 The Working Group on Innovation (INNO WG) was set-up in 2013 in order “to propose to the Forum the broad lines of a strategic plan for an industry-oriented cooperation” of the Research Infrastructures (RIs), ESFRI Scripta Volume III, Innovation-oriented cooperation of Research Infrastructures European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures Innovation Working Group, ISBN PDF: 978-88-943243-1-0
- 36 <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-facility/open-access/framework>
- 37 ARIADNE, 2016, D2.4: Final Innovation Agenda and Action Plan, <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources> (accessed, February 2018)
- 38 An additional bias of this survey derives from the nature of the E-RIHS community itself, which deals predominantly with analytical measurements on materials, objects and monuments and in particular from the side of those providing this type of service.
- 39 <http://www.oecd.org/innovation/policyplatform/48136121.pdf>
- 40 <http://industria.enea.it/technology-transfer-and-exploitation>
- 41 <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/actions-sustainable-and-competitive-open-innovation-ecosystem-eu-us-perspective>
- 42 P. Pouli et al, Heritage Science 4 (1), 9, 2016; doi.org/10.1186/s40494-016-0077
- 43 <http://www.rich2020.eu/about>